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Timing of magmatic processes and unrest associated with mafic historical monogenetic eruptions in Tenerife Island

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3 **Timing of magmatic processes and unrest associated with mafic historical monogenetic**
4 **eruptions in Tenerife Island**
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ABSTRACT

The historical eruptive activity on Tenerife (Canary Islands, Spain) consists of relatively mafic magmas that produced mildly explosive monogenetic eruptions; this is the most likely style of eruption that might occur in the near future. Here we investigate the processes and time scales that lead to such eruptions with the aim to better interpret volcanic unrest in the island and improve eruption forecasts. We combine geochemical and petrological information with a compilation of accounts of seismicity for the historical eruptions of Siete Fuentes, Fasnía, and Arafo. These occurred between December 1704 and February 1705 along the NE rift of Tenerife from three different vents at different altitudes, and more than 10 km apart from each other. The erupted volume increased with time from about $1 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3$ for Siete Fuentes, through $7 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3$ for Fasnía, to $28 \times 10^6 \text{ m}^3$ for Arafo. All the erupted magmas were basanitic; the bulk-rock compositions became more mafic with time due to accumulation of olivine with Cr-spinel inclusions and clinopyroxene, rather than to the arrival of a truly more primitive melt. We have identified four olivine compositional populations (crystal cores at $Fo = 79-80$, $Fo = 81-82$, $Fo = 83-84$, and $Fo = 85-87$; $Fo = 100 \times \text{Mg}/[\text{Mg}+\text{Fe}]$) that are either unzoned, normally or reversely zoned in major and minor elements. The variety of olivine core populations and zoning patterns reflects mixing and mingling between different magmas; their proportions changed with time from Siete Fuentes to Arafo. Clinopyroxene crystals also show a variety of zoning patterns and changes in Mg/Fe and Cr contents indicative of open system magma interactions, but are more difficult to interpret because of fast disequilibrium growth conditions. Modelling of the zoning profiles of olivine shows that early mixing occurred between two relatively evolved magmas, probably at shallow depths one year prior to the eruption. Another mixing event between two more primitive magmas stored presumably at deeper levels occurred less than two months prior to the eruption. Finally, movement from depth of the pre-mixed primitive melts and interaction with the also pre-

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3 mixed, shallower and more evolved melts occurred only two weeks before the eruption.
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5 Although the first and last eruptions were fed by the same magma, each also records renewed
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7 magma movement from depth and mixing before eruption and thus they were probably fed by
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9 different dike systems. The shorter transport times of weeks are also seen in our compilation
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11 of the historical accounts of seismicity associated with these eruptions. The sequence of
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13 events and their timing should be useful for interpretation of monitoring data of unrest in
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15 Tenerife, and the short times between the last processes before eruption could be considered
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17 for the implementation of emergency plans during volcanic crises.
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23 KEY WORDS: monogenetic; diffusion modelling; magma mixing; olivine; Tenerife; unrest.
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INTRODUCTION

Monogenetic volcanic fields typically consist of tens to thousands of individual, small (<1 km³) volcanic edifices (Hasenaka & Carmichael, 1985; Siebe *et al.*, 2004; Kereszturi & Nemeth, 2012) of broadly basaltic compositions (e.g. Hasenaka & Carmichael, 1985; Hsu & Chen, 1998; Mattsson & Oskarsson, 2005; Pérez-López *et al.*, 2011; Sohn *et al.*, 2012) which erupt over periods of hours to decades (e.g. Johnson *et al.*, 2008; Pérez-López *et al.*, 2011; Rowe *et al.*, 2011). The individual eruptions are typically spaced in time and a given monogenetic volcanic field can be active for millions of years (e.g. Hasenaka & Carmichael, 1985; Rodríguez *et al.*, 2010; Kereszturi & Nemeth, 2012). Monogenetic volcanoes *sensu stricto* have been interpreted as the result of a single magma batch based on eruption phenomenology (e.g. Hasenaka & Carmichael, 1985; Pérez-López *et al.*, 2011; Rowe *et al.*, 2011); however, recent studies show that a single eruption can display geochemical evolution, which requires multiple magma batches to be involved (e.g. Smith *et al.*, 2008; Brenna *et al.*, 2010; Needham *et al.*, 2011; Rowe *et al.*, 2011; McGee *et al.*, 2012; Sohn *et al.*, 2012).

Compared to the many existing sets of monitoring data from composite stratovolcanoes or calderas, very few data exist for monogenetic eruptions, despite their abundance in a wide range of tectonic settings (see Kereszturi & Nemeth, 2012). For example, for the Mexican Paricutin (1943) and Jorullo (1759) eruptions, the Ito-Oki (1989) eruption in Japan or the Eldfell (1973) eruption in Iceland, despite the existence of some detailed studies (Yokoyama & Cruz-Reyna, 1990; Rowe *et al.*, 2011; Johnson *et al.*, 2008; Yamamoto *et al.*, 1991; Ukawa, 1993; Mattsson & Oskarsson, 2005; Higgins & Roberge, 2007), there are no integrated monitoring and petrological data sets. The most recent eruption of El Hierro in the Canary Islands is probably the only example with a complete monitoring and petrological dataset (López *et al.*, 2012; Martí *et al.*, 2013a; 2013b). Most of the other

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3 information that exists corresponds to eruptions with a mixed behaviour monogenetic-central
4 volcano, such as the recent eruptions in Iceland (Sigmundsson *et al.*, 2010), or the many flank
5 eruptions that have occurred in recent years on Etna, Sicily
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10 This lack of information makes monogenetic volcanism more difficult to predict than
11 central volcanism. The example of the El Hierro eruption of 2011 is illustrative of our lack of
12 understanding of unrest associated with monogenetic eruptions: after three months of seismic
13 unrest that migrated laterally for more than 20 km at 15 km depth, magma erupted at an
14 unexpected location, with the eruption preceded by 1.5 days of complete seismic calm (Martí
15 *et al.*, 2013b). The presence of a long lived, shallow magma reservoir that controls the stress
16 field associated with large stratovolcanoes is a significant contrast with monogenetic
17 volcanism. In the latter, magma may travel substantial distances from the source region or
18 from intermediate magma storage reservoirs and its path to the surface will be controlled by
19 stress barriers and other discontinuities within the lithosphere.
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32 The geological history of the island of Tenerife has been characterised by the
33 coexistence of monogenetic and central volcanism. The most recent monogenetic volcanism
34 has occurred along two main rift zones, oriented NE and NW and a volcanic field in the south
35 (Geyer & Marti, 2010) (Fig. 1). All of the historical eruptive activity recorded on Tenerife
36 belongs to the monogenetic type, with at least seven eruptions identified since 1492 (Romero,
37 1991; Carracedo *et al.*, 2007). However, the characteristics of these eruptions remain largely
38 unknown, despite the existence of eyewitness descriptions (Sanchez, 2014) and well
39 preserved outcrops for most of them, which together could provide an interesting set of data
40 for interpreting the unrest episodes and the associated eruptions. Most previous studies are
41 descriptive and refer to morphometric analysis (e.g. Dóniz *et al.*, 2008) and have considered
42 these eruptive episodes as simple injections of dykes (e.g. Carracedo, 2008). In order to
43 advance our knowledge of monogenetic volcanism, and in particular the conditions leading to
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3 such eruptions, we have studied the petrology and geochemistry of three monogenetic
4 historical eruptions on Tenerife, the Siete Fuentes, Fasnía, and Arafo eruptions. These
5 occurred between December 1704 and February 1705 along the NE rift zone. By studying
6 these eruptions we aim to elucidate the magmatic processes involved as well as their time
7 scales.
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14 First we describe the geochemical and mineralogical characteristics of samples from
15 the eruptive products of the three eruptions. We then evaluate the evidence for equilibrium
16 between the phenocryst minerals and the magma and establish the thermobarometric
17 conditions. Finally, we model the diffusion profiles of Mg-Fe, Ni and Ca within the olivine
18 crystals to identify the processes that created them and calculate the corresponding time
19 scales. We show that these eruptions correspond to different pulses of magma intruded in the
20 NE rift that underwent multiple mixing episodes during their transport to the surface. We then
21 relate our results to historical accounts of seismic activity associated with the eruptions.
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34 **MONOGENETIC VOLCANOES IN TENERIFE AND THE STUDIED ERUPTIONS**

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36 Tenerife is one of the largest active volcanic systems on Earth, resulting from the superposition of
37 two complex volcanic edifices: an initial volcanic shield representing 90% of the total volume
38 of the island and a basaltic to phonolitic central complex developed on top of it (Martí *et al.*,
39 1994; Carracedo *et al.*, 2007) (Fig. 1). Construction of these two edifices is interspersed with
40 several, large, destructive events that modified their original morphology resulting in the
41 formation of a large caldera (Las Cañadas caldera) in the centre of the island and large
42 landslides (Güímar, La Orotava, Icod valleys) on the flanks. In addition, the construction of
43 Tenerife has been accompanied by abundant monogenetic volcanism, distributed along two
44 rift systems (SRZ or NW rift and DRZ or NE rift), and a large monogenetic field in the south
45 of the island (SVZ) (Fig. 1) (Geyer & Martí, 2010). All historical activity on the island
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3 consists of monogenetic mafic eruptions: Boca Cangrejo (1492), Siete Fuentes (1704), Fasnía
4 (1705), Arafo (1705), Garachico (1706), Chaorra (1798) and Chinyero (1909) (Fig. 1).
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7 We focus here on three of the historical eruptions: Siete Fuentes (SF; December 31
8 1704-January 5 1705), Fasnía (F; January 5-January 15 1705) and Arafo (A; February 2-
9 March 27 1705). The eruptions occurred along a NE trending fracture that is more or less
10 parallel to the NE rift, Fig. 1. The Siete Fuentes and Fasnía vents are only 800 m apart, whilst
11 the Arafo vent is 10 km to the NE. Siete Fuentes and Fasnía are the western and central
12 eruptive vents, and are located at around 2255 m a.s.l. close to the SE ridge of the Las
13 Cañadas (LC) caldera, whereas the Arafo vent is at a lower elevation (about 1500 m a.s.l) at
14 the head of the Güimar Valley (Fig. 1). The erupted volume increased with time from about
15 1.3 x10⁶ m³ for Siete Fuentes, through 6.5 x10⁶ m³ for Fasnía, to 27.5 x10⁶ m³ for Arafo
16 (Carracedo, 2008). Our samples were obtained from the interiors of lava flows to avoid
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34 **METHODOLOGY**

35 **Analytical methods**

36 Whole-rocks were analysed by X-Ray Fluorescence at the University of Washington, USA,
37 using a ThermoARL Advant'XP+ automated sequential wavelength spectrometer. Relative
38 precision of XRF major element analyses is about 0.5 % for SiO₂, TiO₂, Al₂O₃, FeO*, and
39 CaO, and about 1.2-1.7 % for MnO, MgO, Na₂O, K₂O, and P₂O₅ (2 sigma) and other trace
40 elements.
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49 Backscattered electron images, X-Ray distribution maps, and quantitative analyses of
50 the different phases were obtained by electron microprobe using a Cameca SX-50 at the
51 University of Barcelona, and at Nanyang Technological University using a Jeol JXA-8530F
52 Field Emission Gun. Mineral standards were used in both instruments, using 20 or 15 kV
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3 accelerating voltage and 20 to 30 nA beam current. Rim to core, or rim to rim electron
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5 microprobe traverses were performed on crystals with a spacing of 2 to 4 micrometers. We do
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7 not know the size of the convolution effect but given the sharpness of the chemical changes
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9 across phase boundaries during our electron microprobe traverses it should be <4
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11 micrometers. Detailed concentration profiles for Si, Fe, Mg, Mn, Ca and Ni were measured by
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13 electron microprobe for 35 olivine phenocrysts and for Si, Al, Fe, Mg, Mn, Ca, Ti, Na and Cr
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15 in 24 clinopyroxene phenocrysts and eight microphenocrysts.
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19 In addition to BSE imaging of phenocryst zoning, we also obtained large-scale X-Ray
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21 maps (9000 x 9000 μm) using the Jeol JXA-8530F microprobe in WDS mode. These were
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23 transformed into quantitative forsterite content maps [$\text{Fo}=100*\text{Mg}/(\text{Mg}+\text{Fe})$] using the
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25 software MATLAB. Image analysis with MATLAB allows us to elaborate the maps, with the
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27 different mineral phases identified and to quantify the abundance of each mineral phase. The
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29 combination of the olivine distribution maps with the Fo maps generates images in which it is
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31 easier to identify the possible range of olivine populations within the samples from the three
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33 eruptions.
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37 Electron backscattered diffraction (EBSD) patterns of olivine were obtained at the
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39 Nanyang Technological University using a JEOL JSM-7600F equipped with an Oxford/HKL
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41 detector and HKL CHANNEL5 software. In total 13 determinations were successful, since
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43 the EBSD method only works when surface conditions are optimal.
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47 **Diffusion modelling methods**

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49 We modelled the Fe-Mg, Ni and Ca concentration gradients within phenocrysts using the
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51 program DIPRA (Girona & Costa, 2013). This program numerically solves the diffusion
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53 equation for a concentration dependent diffusion coefficient and finds a best-fit taking into
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55 account the analytical error. It incorporates the diffusion coefficients (D) for Fe-Mg from
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3 Dohmen & Chakraborty (2007a, b), Ni from Petry *et al.* (2004) and Ca from Coogan *et al.*
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5 (2005). We solved the diffusion equation with DIPRA for a traverse parallel to the *c* axis.
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7 Since anisotropy of diffusion is strong we have corrected the resultant values with the *D*
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9 parallel to the electron microprobe traverse. We calculated the *D* along the traverse according
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11 to equation 5 in Costa & Chakraborty (2004):
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$$D_i^{traverse} = D_i^a(\cos\alpha)^2 + D_i^b(\cos\beta)^2 + D_i^c(\cos\gamma)^2$$

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16 where α , β and γ are the angles between the *a*, *b* and *c* axes and the electron microprobe
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18 traverse obtained by EBSD. We report the uncertainty on diffusion times that accounts for
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20 analytical, temperature and oxygen fugacity uncertainty as calculated by DIPRA (Girona &
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22 Costa, 2013) after the anisotropy correction. For the initial and boundary conditions we used
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24 various strategies as explained below.
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30 **WHOLE-ROCK CHEMISTRY AND PETROLOGY**

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32 Whole-rock chemical compositions of the three eruptions are basanitic (according to the
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34 classification of Le Maitre *et al.* (1989); Table 1). The Siete Fuentes and Fasnía rocks have
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36 compositions that are virtually within analytical error (MgO = 7.6 wt %, Al₂O₃ = 15 wt %, Ni
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38 =105 ppm, Cr= 200 ppm, Sr = 950) . The Arafo bulk-rock is more mafic, with higher MgO
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40 (9.4 wt %), Ni (180 ppm) and Cr (330 ppm), and lower Al₂O₃ (14.1 wt %) and Sr (880 ppm).
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42 Ratios of incompatible elements in the bulk-rocks of the three eruptions practically overlap
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44 with each other (Zr/Y = 10.5 to 10.6; La/Y= 1.9 to 2.1) (Fig. 2). As we will show
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46 subsequently, the Arafo bulk-rock can be explained by accumulation of olivine with Cr-spinel
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48 inclusions and clinopyroxene in a melt composition similar to that of the Siete Fuentes and
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50 Fasnía magmas, rather than being a more primitive melt (Fig. 2).
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54 The three eruptions contain the same phenocryst mineral assemblage and exhibit
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56 similar textures. Phenocrysts (> 300 μ m in the shortest dimension) and microphenocrysts (100
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3 to 300 μm in the shortest dimension) are of olivine and clinopyroxene, typically occurring as
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5 isolated crystals. Both minerals tend to be euhedral and contain inclusions of Fe-Ti oxides of
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7 variable composition. Some olivine crystals (less than 10%) have skeletal shapes.
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9 Backscattered electron images (BSE) and quantitative X-Ray maps show that many olivine
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11 crystals are zoned in Fe and Mg (Figs 3a-c). Clinopyroxene phenocrysts can have large pools
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13 of matrix glass in their interiors and show rims of different composition to the cores (Fig.4a).
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15 BSE images and X-Ray maps show that Cpx can have very complex zoning patterns,
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17 including sector zoning, patchy and dissolution zones, and oscillatory zoning (Figs 3d-f and
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19 4). Plagioclase is less abundant and occurs in the groundmass only. The groundmass is made
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21 of microlites of olivine, clinopyroxene, plagioclase, and Fe-Ti oxides. The modal abundance
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23 of each phase was computed with image analyses and by the point-counting method (Table
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25 1), and is reported vesicle-free; this was converted to wt % using mineral densities.
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27 Phenocryst abundance increases from about 7 wt % in Siete Fuentes (Ol = 3.3 wt %, Cpx =
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29 3.4 wt %), through about 13 wt % in Fasnía (Ol = 6.5 wt %, Cpx = 6.3), to about 18 wt % in
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31 Arafo (Ol = 8.4, Cpx = 9.8 wt %). Olivine and clinopyroxene microlite abundances increase
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33 from Siete Fuentes to Arafo, whereas plagioclase and oxide microlite abundances decrease
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35 (Table 1).
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43 **MINERAL COMPOSITION AND CHEMICAL ZONING**

44 **Olivine**

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46 Olivine core compositions in the products of the three eruptions range between Fo_{79} and Fo_{87}
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48 ($\text{Fo} = 100 \times \text{Mg} / [\text{Mg} + \text{Fe}^*]$, where Fe^* is total iron) (Table 2). Three main core populations are
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50 observed with compositional plateaus at Fo_{79-80} , Fo_{81-82} , and Fo_{85-87} , except for one crystal
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52 with a core at Fo_{83-84} (Fig. 5). This variety of core compositions suggests that at least there
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54 were three magmas or magmatic environments that were involved in the generation of these
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3 eruptions (e.g., Kahl *et al.*, 2011). The last 5-20 micrometers of almost all crystals show
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5 strongly decreasing Fo contents and a wide range of rim composition from Fo₆₃ to Fo₈₁. Rim
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7 compositions with Fo contents lower than 77-78, are mainly found in the Fasnía samples, and
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9 have been considered to be the result of fast growth (see following sections). The Fo profiles
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11 (Fig. 6) show that phenocrysts can be virtually unzoned, normally zoned with decreasing Fo
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13 content towards the rim, reversely zoned (increasing Fo content towards the rim), or more
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15 complexly zoned including reverse followed by normal zoning. Unzoned and normally zoned
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17 crystals are the most abundant. Crystal cores and zoning patterns are more variable in the first
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19 eruption of Siete Fuentes, which also lacks the most evolved population of low Fo cores (79-
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21 80). Fasnía and Arafo have the three core populations Fo₇₉₋₈₀, Fo₈₁₋₈₂, and Fo₈₅₋₈₇ and very
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23 similar zoning patterns.
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28 The CaO and the NiO contents of the olivine range from 0.14 to 0.6 wt % and from
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30 0.03 to 0.33 wt %, respectively. The olivine crystals are all reversely zoned in CaO, whereas
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32 the NiO profiles follow the trend of Fo. Olivine core compositions range between CaO 0.14-
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34 0.28 wt % and NiO 0.16-0.29 wt % in Siete Fuentes, CaO 0.23-0.28 wt % and NiO 0.1-0.28
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36 wt % in Fasnía, and CaO 0.18-0.28 wt % and NiO 0.1-0.33 wt % in Arafo. The variation of Ni
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38 at a given Fo content is similar for all crystals and eruptions (Fig. 7). This probably reflects
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40 that Fo and Ni behave in a similar manner during magma evolution and mixing, and also have
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42 similar volume diffusion rates (e.g. Chakraborty, 2010). In contrast, there is a much larger
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44 variation of Ca concentration for a given Fo content (Fig. 7); for example, from about 0.12 to
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46 about 0.26 wt % CaO for Fo₈₅. The variation is also more extreme in olivines from the first
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48 eruption of Siete Fuentes than the rest. Such large variations in Ca content at a given Fo
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50 implies a variety of magmas from different mantle sources (e.g., Strong & Wolff, 2003) or
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52 different melting conditions. It seems possible that the first erupted magma of Siete Fuentes
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54 simply picked up a larger variety of crystals as it opened a path on its way to the surface. The
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3 variation in the Ca content may also be the result of very different diffusive re-equilibration
4 rates for Ca vs Fe-Mg (Ca diffuses significantly slower than Fe-Mg; Chakraborty, 2010).
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8 9 **Clinopyroxene**

10 Clinopyroxene crystals are complexly zoned, including core to rim variations, but also exhibit
11 oscillatory, sector, and patchy zoning (Fig. 4). Representative chemical compositions and
12 structural formulae calculated according to Deer *et al.* (1992) show that they are ferroan
13 titanian augite, with $Wo_{45-51}En_{35-45}Fs_{10-17}$, and $Mg\#^*$ ($Mg\#^* = 100 \times Mg/[Mg+Fe^*]$) ranging
14 from about 69 to 82. A structural formula based on 6 oxygens and hence an idealised 4
15 cations to check for charge balance highlights that many crystals appear to have a large
16 calculated Fe^{3+} content (Table 3). If we only use the Fe^{2+} to calculate the $Mg\#$
17 ($=100 \times Mg/[Mg+Fe^{2+}]$, where Fe^{2+} was calculated from the structural formula) values increase
18 to 75-95. Core to rim, or rim to rim traverses show that there are abrupt changes in
19 composition, sometimes with high $Mg\#^*$ being positively correlated with high Cr contents,
20 likely reflecting the arrival of more primitive melt (Fig. 8). Other crystals however, show low
21 $Mg\#^*$ but high Cr in the rims. Generally, TiO_2 content increases from the cores to the rims,
22 reaching the highest values in the Arafo clinopyroxene. The large Ti X-Ray maps (Figs 3d-f)
23 illustrate well the oscillatory and sector zoning of the Cpx, and its greater abundance from
24 Siete Fuentes to Arafo. The shapes, textures and large variety of zoning patterns and
25 variations in minor elements shown by the clinopyroxene suggest that in addition to mingling
26 or mixing they have been affected by growth kinetics. The high calculated proportion of Fe^{3+}
27 in clinopyroxene has been suggested by Mollo *et al.* (2010) to reflect clinopyroxene growth
28 kinetics rather than the local oxidation state. This hampers the use of clinopyroxene
29 compositions to obtain reliable pressure and temperature constraints.
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DISCUSSION

Assessing the effects of crystal accumulation and geothermobarometric calculations

The whole-rock compositions show similar ratios of incompatible elements, but the major elements seem to suggest that the eruptions became progressively more mafic from Siete Fuentes to Arafo (i.e. MgO increases from 7.5 to 9.4 wt %). To understand the processes, magma sources and plumbing systems for these eruptions it is important to establish if different magma types were actually involved over time. We tested these possibilities by a combination of mass-balance calculations and crystal-liquid equilibrium thermodynamic calculations.

First, the Mg-Fe equilibrium between olivine and bulk-rock was tested using the equation of Roeder & Emslie (1970) (Fig. 9). We calculated the equilibrium Mg# at the fO_2 (oxygen fugacity) of the NNO buffer (see below). We found that the Fo >83-84 cores of crystals from Siete Fuentes and Fasnía are too Mg-rich to have grown from their host magma (proxied by the bulk-rock) and thus are xenocrystic (probably antecrysts). In contrast, the Fo₈₀₋₈₂ cores are in equilibrium with the Siete Fuentes bulk-rock which also has the lowest phenocryst content and thus it is the most likely representative of a liquid composition. The cores with lower Fo (at around 79-80) would be in equilibrium with slightly more evolved liquids. The compositions of such liquids can be obtained by the subtraction of the observed modal proportions of phenocrysts from the Siete Fuentes whole-rock (i.e. the matrix composition of the bulk-rock). The olivine cores with Fo >83-84 are in equilibrium with a magma similar to the Arafo bulk-rock. However, Arafo itself has the highest phenocryst content and thus the high Mg/Fe of the whole-rock could also be due to the addition of olivine, clinopyroxene and spinel. This possibility is consistent with the fact that despite the

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3 higher Mg# of the whole-rock the olivine cores have the same Fo content as the olivine cores
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5 from Siete Fuentes and Fasnía.

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7 Mass balance calculations show that addition of only 0.6 wt % of olivine and 0.5 wt %
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9 of clinopyroxene to the Siete Fuentes composition satisfactorily reproduces the Fasnía bulk-
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11 rock, suggesting that this magma was basically the same as Siete Fuentes. Moreover, addition
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13 of 5.7 wt % of olivine and 2.9 wt % of clinopyroxene to the Siete Fuentes bulk-rock also
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15 reproduces the Arafo bulk-rock (Supplementary Data Electronic Appendix 3; Fig. 9). Thus,
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17 the Arafo original liquid (without xenocrysts) is in equilibrium with Fo₈₀₋₈₂ olivine, like the
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19 Siete Fuentes and Fasnía liquids. We conclude that the Arafo eruptive episode was fuelled by
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21 a magma similar to the first erupted bulk-rock composition of Siete Fuentes, and that the
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23 Fasnía and Arafo eruptions were driven by the same magma that accumulated some olivine
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25 and clinopyroxene crystals. Note that the highest Fo crystals could be in equilibrium with the
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27 Arafo bulk-rock, but the rock contains mainly low Fo crystals. Crystal accumulation could
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29 have occurred either during transport and residence in the shallow crust, or could be directly
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31 inherited from a part of the magma reservoir that contained slightly higher amounts of
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33 phenocrysts.
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39 Given that the Siete Fuentes rocks have the lowest phenocryst content we have tested
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41 using the MELTS algorithm (Ghiorso & Sack, 1995) the conditions at which olivine Fo₈₀₋₈₂
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43 could have grown. We also considered the presence of clinopyroxene and absence of
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45 plagioclase close to the liquidus in these calculations. We found that for a melt with the Siete
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47 Fuentes bulk-rock composition and fO_2 close to the NNO oxygen buffer, we reproduce the
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49 mineral assemblage and olivine composition at a pressure range of 0.2-0.5 GPa, an H₂O
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51 content in the melt of 1-2 wt %, and a temperature of 1175±15°C. We used the olivine-based
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53 geothermometer of Putirka *et al.* (2007) which gave a temperature of 1168-1193°C at a
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55 pressure range of 0.2-0.5 GPa and an H₂O content in the melt of 1-2 wt %. These
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3 temperatures are in agreement with those obtained from MELTS. We also tried to calculate
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5 what would be the conditions of equilibrium of the olivine with Fo contents between 87-83.
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7 For this, we first note that we know that the Mg# of the liquid was the same as the Arafo
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9 bulk-rock. Moreover, the high Fo of these olivine crystals cannot simply be due to a different
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11 fO_2 , since they also have higher Ni and lower Ca contents, and thus they grew from more
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13 primitive, hotter liquids. Thus we have simply used the Arafo bulk-rock composition as a
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15 proxy for a more primitive magma to perform the MELTS calculations. We note that we are
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17 not assuming here that the Arafo magma that erupted was a liquid, simply that a more
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19 primitive magma with the equilibrium Mg# of the high-Fo crystals would be similar to Arafo.
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21 The Arafo bulk-rock is a combination of accumulated low Fo crystals and liquid (see above).
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23 We obtained similar water contents (1-1.5 H₂O wt %), slightly higher pressures (0.4-0.6 GPa),
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25 and significantly higher temperature (1245±15°C). These ranges of conditions for olivines
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27 with different compositions are important because they will be used to calculate the diffusion
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29 coefficients and thus time scales in the following sections.
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34 An accurate estimation of pressure and temperature from the clinopyroxene was not
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36 possible because we did not find that the bulk-rock was in equilibrium with the clinopyroxene
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38 using the criteria of Putirka (2008). This is likely to be due to the high calculated Fe³⁺ in the
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40 clinopyroxenes which probably reflects the effects of fast growth and strong sector zoning
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42 shown by the crystals and reported in other experimental and field studies (Mollo *et al.*,
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44 2010).
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49 **Magma plumbing system**

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51 Several studies (e.g. Brenna *et al.*, 2010; Needham *et al.*, 2011; Sohn *et al.*, 2012) have
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53 pointed out that given the ranges of magma compositions within a monogenetic eruption they
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55 cannot be fuelled from a single magma reservoir. In the case of Tenerife it appears that the
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3 three eruptions were driven mainly by the same magma that accumulated crystals with time or
4 that sampled a part of the reservoir that was richer in crystals. However, the erupted magma
5 was generated by mixing and mingling of crystals and melts from various sources as recorded
6 by the variety of Fo zoning patterns, and Ni and Ca concentrations at a given Fo content.
7 Moreover, the heterogeneity of the Ti X-Ray large scale map (Fig. 3f) suggests mixing and
8 mingling might have also occurred during eruption, although we cannot rule out the
9 possibility that some post-eruptive crystallization also played a role.
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18 The compositions of the olivine cores with large plateaus suggest that there were at
19 least two well-defined magmatic environments that interacted to create the erupted magma
20 compositions: one where the Fo_{81-82} and Fo_{79-80} grew, and another one where the highest Fo
21 (85-87 and 83-84) crystals grew. Note that the range of Ca concentrations at high Fo contents
22 implies either a range of mantle-derived mafic magmas from different sources and thus
23 different composition and intensive variables, or different degrees of re-equilibration by
24 diffusion for prolonged periods of time. We argue that these two environments were
25 heterogeneous to some extent because there is about 3-4 mol% variation of Fo content in the
26 olivine core plateaux. With two such environments, the zoning profiles of olivine suggest
27 three magma mixing/mingling events: (1) M1, mixing between olivine crystals with Fo_{81-82}
28 and olivine crystals with Fo_{79-80} . This would involve interactions between evolved basalts
29 probably in the shallow crust. These magmas may be fractionated from previous intrusions of
30 more primitive melts; (2) M2, mixing between olivine crystals with Fo_{85-87} and olivine
31 crystals with Fo_{83-84} within the most mafic environment, which was likely also to be the
32 deepest; (3) M3, intrusion and associated mixing of the more mafic magma in a shallower and
33 more evolved reservoir, followed by ascent to the surface (Fig. 10).
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54 In the above scenario, we consider that the more evolved melts that were stored in the
55 shallower parts of the system were the products of successive injections of magma that were
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3 unable to erupt, probably due to lack of buoyancy (i. e. failed eruptions; Moran et al., 2011).
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5 We propose that because of the impossibility of accommodating magma at a given depth after
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7 the two first inputs (first mixing process), a deeper new accumulation level was created. Two
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9 inputs of magma occurred here (second mixing process) prior to ascent. Below we show that
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11 this is consistent with the longer residence times calculated for the evolved olivine crystals in
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13 the shallower magma (around 400 days), and the shorter times calculated for crystals at
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15 deeper levels (around one month).
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19 To explain the presence of olivine with a homogeneous Fo content next to olivine with
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21 complex zoning we considered the generation of coherent and active regions due to the
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23 mixing and mingling processes in two magma storage regions located at different depths (Fig.
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25 10). This means that even if the mixing process comprises the whole magma reservoir there
26
27 was not complete homogenisation. Coherent regions represent portions of the original magma
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29 in which the olivine crystals are in equilibrium with the liquid. Active regions represent the
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31 more effectively mingled areas with consequent chemical mixing. In these latter areas the
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33 olivine crystals develop normal or reverse zoning. The presence of coherent and active
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35 regions has been described before in several studies (Perugini *et al.*, 2003b; Perugini & Poli,
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37 2012; Albert *et al.*, 2014) and such magma mixing processes have also been simulated
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39 numerically (Perugini *et al.*, 2003a, 2004; Petrelli *et al.*, 2006). Since the magmas involved in
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41 the mixing are basalts with probably very similar compositions, coherent and active regions
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43 cannot be clearly distinguished. .
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49 **Time scales of magmatic processes**

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51 Representative olivine crystals were selected to calculate the time scales of the mixing
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53 processes according to chemical diffusion (e.g. Costa *et al.*, 2008). The initial and boundary
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55 conditions were chosen to represent the different core plateau compositions and the observed
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3 composition at the rim. All the crystals with normal or reverse Fo zoning show a good fit for
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5 two boundary conditions after the initial condition (plateau 1) (Table 4). The initial conditions
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7 were the core plateaus at a given concentration of Fo. For all zoning types we used step-like
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9 initial conditions because those fitted better the compositional profiles. In addition, we also
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11 modelled the Ni and Ca concentrations of some crystals (Fig. 11). Olivine crystals from
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13 Fasnia (the second eruption) are characterised by very low Fo rims (Figs 5 and 6) which likely
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15 represent the final fast growth of these crystals during ascent. Although our choice of initial
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17 and boundary conditions is non-unique, we decided to model the Fe-Mg variation as well as
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19 possible and then impose the same initial (e.g. number of plateaus) and boundary conditions
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21 for the rest of the elements. This is because the diffusivities and analytical precision are much
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23 better known and better, respectively, for Fe-Mg than other elements. This means that the
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25 models for Fe-Mg, Ni, and Ca are self-consistent. Another option would have been to obtain
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27 the best fit possible for each element independently and then discuss why we needed different
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29 initial and boundary conditions for each. In any case, the time differences between the
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31 possible ranges of initial and boundary conditions that are a good match to the data are small
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33 and typically within error.
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39 In total we determined three different times (Table 4), although each individual crystal
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41 records two times: Time 1 is the first mixing event that occurred in the shallow reservoir
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43 (M1), Time 2 is for the second mixing event in the deeper reservoir (M2) and Time 3 is the
44
45 last event involving mixing between the two already mixed magmas (M3). Time 1 is the
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47 longest (Fig. 12a) of about a year and is recorded by olivines with Fo₇₉₋₈₂ cores. Time 2 is less
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49 than three months, corresponding to olivine with Fo₈₃₋₈₇ cores, and Time 3 (Fig. 12b) is
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51 around two weeks for all crystals, with somewhat longer times in the last eruption. The times
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53 determined from Fo, Ni and Ca –for olivine with Fo₈₃₋₉₀- are consistent and are within error
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55 according to Costa & Dungan (2005), except for some times for Ca. This might be because
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3 the diffusion coefficient has been calibrated for olivine with $F_{O_{83-90}}$ (Coogan *et al.*, 2005) or
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5 the longer times for Ca could be reflecting that part of the profile is due to crystallization and
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7 not only diffusion.
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10 We subtracted the calculated mixing times from the known eruption dates to infer the
11 intrusion/mixing dates of the magma batches (Fig. 13) and to test whether the crystals from
12 the older eruptions have diffused for proportionally longer times. This relationship can be
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14 expected if all eruptions were fed by the same magma (e.g. Kahl *et al.*, 2011) with no
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16 additional mixing between eruptions. We find that early intrusion and mixing occurred
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18 sometime between September 1703 and February 1704. The second mixing event in the deep
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20 reservoir occurred sometime between October 1704 and middle January 1705; this means that
21
22 there was an additional remobilization of magma at depth after the beginning of the Siete
23
24 Fuentes eruption (December 31) recorded in the olivine crystals from Arafo. Finally, the last
25
26 mixing occurred a few weeks before each eruption, indicating that at least two different inputs
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28 of magma occurred sometime between December 17-31, and January 19-February 2. The first
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30 input would be responsible of triggering the eruptions of Siete Fuentes and, 5 days later, of
31
32 Fasnía. The last magma transfer and mixing occurred one month later, and reactivated the
33
34 system by making a new dike that lead to the eruption of Arafo. Thus, although the three
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36 events were fed by the same magmas, each was activated by renewed magma migration from
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38 depth and mixing. This implies that at least the first and last eruptions were fed by different
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40 dike systems rather than ‘aging’ of the Siete Fuentes magma batch with time at shallow
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42 depths followed by transport to the Arafo eruption site. These dates can be used to compare to
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44 the monitoring or unrest data as we show below.
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54 **Historical accounts of unrest and their relation to magmatic processes**

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3 Our petrological study of eruptive products from Siete Fuentes, Fasnía and Arafo provides
4 important information about pre-eruptive processes and time scales associated with
5 monogenetic eruptions. Correlation of these data with information about precursor unrest
6 activity would be very useful to understand future unrest monitoring signals and contribute to
7 the development of emergency evacuation plans for monogenetic fields. The first seismic
8 station was installed in Tenerife in 1964, and thus for older eruptions we have information
9 only about historical accounts of seismicity. Based on work conducted by Dvorak &
10 Gasparini (1991) and later by Guidoboni & Ciuccarelli (2011) we conducted an exhaustive
11 review of the historical unrest activity for the three studied eruptions based upon original
12 reports compiled in Romero (1991) and Glas (1982). Information extracted from the historical
13 documents (Table 5), includes the dates, the days before and after the eruption and the
14 localities where earthquakes were felt. The reported seismic activity began seven days prior to
15 the first eruption with a swarm of twenty-nine earthquakes over three hours. According to our
16 diffusion modelling results, this event corresponds to the ascent of magma to the surface (Fig.
17 14). On January 21, twelve days prior to the last eruption (Arafo), there was an increase in the
18 seismic activity. One of the stronger earthquakes up to that date was followed by so many
19 strong earthquakes that it was not possible to count them. The day after at least twenty
20 earthquakes occurred (Table 5). This increase in seismicity could imply deep magma mixing
21 and is consistent with the second input of magma proposed by us according to the calculated
22 time scales (Figs 13 and 14).
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47 There are no historical accounts of seismicity that are coincident with the two earlier
48 mixing events that happened one year and ~60 days, respectively, prior to the eruptions. This
49 lack of information could be due to the lack of historical reports or to the lack of felt
50 earthquakes, but we note that seismic unrest at El Hierro did start a few months before the
51 eruption (Martí et al., 2013b). The interpretation of the historical accounts without
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3 considering the magma history revealed by the olivine crystals would lead to erroneous
4 conclusions. The seven days of seismic activity would be related to direct ascent of magma
5 from the source region to the surface, but the first ‘failed eruptions’ (Moran et al., 2011)
6 probably started a few months or years before and these could be detected and properly
7 interpreted by modern monitoring systems.
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13 14 15 16 **CONCLUSIONS**

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18 Three historical mafic monogenetic eruptions that occurred within two months of each other
19 and more than 10 km apart on Tenerife were fed by the same magma that accumulated
20 crystals with time. The three eruptions record the involvement of two distinct magma storage
21 regions in which the more evolved mafic magmas resided and pre-mixed, before a final
22 mixing event that brought them to the surface. The first mixing and mingling event likely
23 occurred at shallow depths and about one year prior to the first eruption. This probably
24 involved differentiated magmas from a more primitive parent that were not able to erupt, most
25 likely because of buoyancy constraints, but they could have been instrumental in pre-
26 conditioning the crust for future eruptions. A second magma mixing/mingling event between
27 two more primitive magmas, and probably located at deeper levels, occurred about two
28 months before the first eruption. A final event of magma transport and mingling occurred
29 because of the movement of the deeper magma to the shallow storage reservoir, followed by
30 transport to the surface in the last two weeks before each eruption. The reported seismicity,
31 compiled from historical documents, lasted on the order of a week and matches our shorter
32 calculated times for the last mixing event and magma transport. The observation that early
33 mixing of more differentiated magmas occurred before the deeper mixing suggests that for
34 monogenetic eruptions to occur it might be necessary to prepare and precondition the crustal
35 column with a series of ‘failed eruptions’ before the magmas can actually reach the surface.
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3 Our findings agree well with the instrumental seismic monitoring of the recent El Hierro
4 eruption and show that a few days to a few months before an eruption a modern seismic
5 network should be able to detect such magma mixing events. The shorter times of a few
6 weeks between the final mixing and transport to the surface should be useful for emergency
7 planning if a new new period of magmatic unrest should occur on the island of Tenerife and
8 perhaps also in other monogenetic fields.
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39 **FIGURE CAPTIONS:**

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42 **Fig. 1.** Distribution of mafic and intermediate (red circles and felsic (black circles) volcanic
43 vents in Tenerife. White stars are the location of all historical eruptions. The vents of the
44 studied eruptions of Siete Fuentes (SF), Fasnía (F) and Arafo (A) are labelled and the extent
45 of their eruptive products is shown in green. The locations where seismic activity was felt
46 before and during the studied eruptions are also labelled: LO, La Orotava; PC, Puerto de la
47 Cruz; LR, Los Realejos; A, Arafo; C, Candelaria; G, Güimar. The dashed lines mark the
48 Santiago Rift Zone (SRZ) and the Dorsal Rift Zone (DRZ). Other abbreviations: SVZ
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3 Southern Volcanic Zone; LC Las Cañadas; T Teide; PV Pico Viejo. Modified from Martí *et*
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5 *al.*, (2011).
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8 **Fig. 2.** Selected major and trace element variation diagrams for the three studied eruptions.
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10 The bulk-rock composition of Arafo can be explained by addition of olivine and
11 clinopyroxene to the Siete Fuentes bulk-rock composition. The black arrows indicate the
12 computed composition obtained by mass balance (numbers next to arrows are the amount of
13 crystals in wt %). Blue symbols - Arafo; green symbols - Fasnía; red symbols - Siete Fuentes.
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20 **Fig. 3.** (a,b,c) Quantitative Fo (mol %) maps obtained by combining two-dimensional Mg
21 and Fe distribution maps with the olivine abundance image (obtained by image processing
22 with MATLAB). The variety of zoning patterns of olivine crystals is apparent (red arrows
23 point to different zoning patterns). It is also apparent how the modal proportion of olivine
24 increases from Siete Fuentes to Arafo. (d,e,f) Two-dimensional Ti distribution maps.
25 Complexly zoned clinopyroxene crystals show core to rim variations, oscillatory and patchy
26 zoning. Rims are enriched in Ti. Red dashed lines in (f) indicate the presence of areas with
27 different composition and thus chemical heterogeneities at the local level. These may indicate
28 syn-eruptive mixing, although it is difficult to know if some post-eruption processes (e.g.
29 variable microlite growth) have also played a role in creating heterogeneity since the samples
30 are from interiors of lava flows.
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46 **Fig. 4.** Back-scattered electron images of one representative clinopyroxene phenocryst (a) and
47 one representative microphenocryst (b). Note the complex zoning of the clinopyroxene with
48 evidence of oscillatory zoning and dissolution surfaces. Red arrow in (b) shows the location
49 of the electron microprobe traverse shown in Fig. 8 (crystal A-microcpx4).
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3 **Fig. 5.** Frequency histograms displaying the distribution of Fo (mol%) in 35 olivine cores and
4 rims from Siete Fuentes (SF), Fasnía (F) and Arafo (A). Lower Fo content cores and rims are
5 mainly present in the Fasnía eruption.
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10 **Fig. 6.** Olivine Fo (mol%) profiles from rim to rim and rim to core from Siete Fuentes, Fasnía
11 and Arafo. (a) Siete Fuentes olivine crystals exhibit larger range of Fo populations (Fo₇₉₋₈₀,
12 Fo₈₁₋₈₂, Fo₈₃₋₈₄ and Fo₈₅₋₈₇). (b, c) Fasnía and Arafo olivine crystals exhibit three Fo
13 populations (Fo₇₉₋₈₀, Fo₈₁₋₈₂ and Fo₈₅₋₈₇). The main difference with the first eruption, Siete
14 Fuentes, is the higher presence of olivine with lower Fo content (Fo₇₉₋₈₀) and the lower Fo
15 values for the rims in Fasnía which are probably due to post-eruption crystallization.
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24 **Fig. 7.** Fo content (mol%) vs. CaO and NiO (wt %) in of olivine crystals. Whereas the NiO
25 vs. Fo plot displays a relatively linear trend, the CaO vs. Fo plot shows different trends for
26 each crystal (see text).
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32 **Fig. 8.** Representative compositional profiles for clinopyroxene phenocrysts and
33 microphenocryst. The location of profile A-microcpx4 is shown in Fig.4b.
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38 **Fig. 9.** Olivine Fo *versus* Mg# bulk-rock equilibrium tested using the equation of Roeder &
39 Emslie (1970). Olivine crystals with Fo₈₁₋₈₂ are in equilibrium with a melt composition close
40 to that of the Siete Fuentes and Fasnía bulk-rocks, indicating that olivines with Fo₈₃₋₈₇ are
41 xenocrysts. Fasnía and Arafo melt compositions have been recalculated by subtracting the
42 olivine (ol) and the clinopyroxene (cpx) compositions from the bulk-rock (see main text). The
43 recalculated compositions (crosses) are in equilibrium with Fo₈₁₋₈₂ olivine. Olivine crystals
44 with Fo>83-84 would be in equilibrium with a melt with the Mg # of the Arafo bulk-rock.
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55 **Fig. 10.** Schematic illustration of the magma chamber processes and plumbing system. The
56 olivine crystals record two magmatic environments and three mixing episodes: (M1) mixing
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3 between olivine with Fo₈₅₋₈₇ and Fo₈₃₋₈₄; (M2) mixing between olivine with Fo₈₁₋₈₂ and Fo₇₉₋
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between olivine with Fo₈₅₋₈₇ and Fo₈₃₋₈₄; (M2) mixing between olivine with Fo₈₁₋₈₂ and Fo₇₉₋
80; (M3) mixing between previous magma batches and ascent to the surface. Olivines with
complex zoning represent active regions which are mingled and mixed, whereas more
homogeneous crystals are from coherent regions in which the original magma was preserved.

Fig. 11. Compositional profiles and diffusion models for two representative olivine crystals. White circles are measured concentrations. Black lines indicate the initial Fo profile shapes and boundaries. Red lines are the best fit diffusion models computed using DIPRA. The orientation of the crystallographic axes (*a*, *b* and *c*) and the traverse (*tr*) are shown as stereographic projections in the lower hemisphere. Fo, Ni and Ca zoning can be fit with two boundary conditions after the initial condition (P1). The first boundary condition can be considered as a second compositional plateau (P2).

Fig. 12. Calculated diffusion times for all the crystals from the three eruptions plotted *versus* the Fo content of the initial and boundary conditions listed in Table 4. Three different magma mixing events are recorded by the crystals as three different times. The third event (b) is common to all the crystals, because it is the one that brings the crystals to the surface. (a) Two groups can be distinguished on the basis of Fo and time. The first (Mixing 1) magma mixing (between Fo₇₉₋₈₂) occurred around one year before the eruption. The second (Mixing 2) magma mixing (between Fo₈₃₋₈₇) happened less than three months prior to the first eruption. (b) Times of the magma transport to the surface (Mixing 3) are one to two weeks.

Fig. 13. Calculated intrusion dates of the different magma batches have been obtained by subtracting the calculated residence times from the known eruption dates. The black dashed line indicates an intrusion followed by an eruption without significant residence of the magma at depth. The continuous black line indicates different residence times of the magma in the reservoir prior to the eruption.

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3 **Fig.14.** Relationship between the timescales obtained by kinetic modelling and the cumulative
4 curve of the days with felt earthquakes during the unrest at Siete Fuentes, Fasnía and Arafo
5 from historical accounts. (a) Calculated times for the mixing events from olivine crystals from
6 Siete Fuentes, Fasnía and Arafo; green diamonds: first mixing event; blue diamonds: second
7 mixing event. Orange diamonds: third mixing event and magma transport to the surface. (b)
8 Cumulative percentage of mixing time events shown in (a) and cumulative percentage of days
9 with felt earthquakes during the unrest of Siete Fuentes, Fasnía and Arafo. White diamonds:
10 individual times calculated times in (a). Black diamonds: days with seismic activity, from
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- Mafic and intermediate monogenetic vents ● Phonolitic vents
- ☆ Historical monogenetic eruptions ■ Eruptive products ⊙ Localities

147x138mm (300 x 300 DPI)

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Table 1: Whole rock chemical compositions and modal abundances

Unit	Siete Fuentes	Fasnia	Arafo
Rock type	Tephrite	Tephrite	Tephrite
Eruption	December 1704	January 1705	February 1705
<i>wt%</i>			
SiO ₂	44.4	44.4	44.0
TiO ₂	3.65	3.70	3.56
Al ₂ O ₃	15.16	14.99	14.10
FeO*	12.10	12.10	12.39
MgO	7.50	7.70	9.40
MnO	0.19	0.19	0.19
CaO	10.67	10.67	10.58
Na ₂ O	3.87	3.82	3.57
K ₂ O	1.59	1.54	1.42
P ₂ O ₅	0.76	0.76	0.72
Total	99.95	99.86	99.94
Mg#	38.3	38.9	43.1
Mg#*	58.1	58.7	62.8
<i>Ppm</i>			
Sc	21.6	20.3	23.2
V	309	308	302
Cr	195	206	331
Ni	103	111	180
Cu	60.2	58.2	60.9
Zn	117	119	116
Ga	20.1	20.8	20.0
Rb	33.3	32.7	30.0
Sr	953	949	883
Y	26.7	26.8	24.8
Zr	284	283	264
Nb	71.3	70.8	65.3
Ba	500	493	457
La	51.7	54.5	53.3
Ce	104	102	99
Nd	52.0	52.8	46.2
Pb	3.9	2.3	3.6
Th	7.5	5.0	5.2
U	2.2	1.90	3.8
Zr/Y	10.64	10.55	10.63
La/Y	1.94	2.03	2.15
<i>Modal abundances in wt% and vesicle free</i>			
<i>Point-counting</i>			
Ol phenocryst	3.3	6.5	8.4
Cpx phenocryst	3.4	6.3	9.8
<i>Image analyses</i>			
Ol tot	5.0	7.7	11.8
Cpx tot	17.7	25.1	20.6
Spl tot	9.7	9.3	4.3
Pl tot	15.9	14.5	8.9

Modal abundances calculated by the point-counting method and by image analyse of the two-dimensional element distribution maps. FeO*=total iron. Mg#*=molar 100xMgO/(MgO+FeO*). Mg#=molar 100xMgO/(MgO+FeO), where the proportion of FeO has been calculated for f_{O_2} =NNO using MELTS.

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For Peer Review

Table 2: Chemical compositions of representative olivine phenocryst cores

Unit	SF	SF	SF	SF	SF	F	F	F	A	A	A	A	A
Grain no.:	ol-1	ol-2	ol-6	ol-11	ol-12	ol-5	ol-11	ol-18	ol-10	ol-11	ol-12	ol-13	ol-14
<i>wt %</i>													
SiO ₂	38.01	39.12	38.89	36.79	38.14	40.13	37.62	39.37	39.33	38.69	39.80	39.35	39.57
FeO*	18.83	15.34	12.38	16.95	14.12	14.55	19.08	13.38	19.40	14.30	13.67	13.67	13.90
MgO	42.7	45.5	47.6	43.7	45.7	45.3	41.5	45.7	41.5	45.1	45.4	45.7	45.2
CaO	0.27	0.15	0.20	0.29	0.15	0.24	0.26	0.28	0.24	0.22	0.22	0.22	0.20
MnO	0.27	0.21	0.12	0.29	0.16	0.16	0.26	0.17	0.30	0.15	0.15	0.20	0.22
NiO	0.17	0.19	0.29	0.23	0.27	0.27	0.15	0.25	0.11	0.00	0.29	0.30	0.32
Total	100.2	100.5	99.5	98.3	98.5	100.7	98.9	99.1	100.9	98.5	99.6	99.4	99.4
<i>O = 4</i>													
Si	0.974	0.982	0.974	0.958	0.973	0.999	0.979	0.993	0.999	0.986	0.999	0.991	0.997
Fe*	0.403	0.322	0.259	0.369	0.301	0.303	0.428	0.282	0.412	0.305	0.287	0.288	0.293
Mg	1.630	1.701	1.779	1.697	1.739	1.682	1.610	1.716	1.573	1.713	1.700	1.714	1.698
Mn	0.006	0.004	0.003	0.006	0.004	0.003	0.006	0.004	0.007	0.003	0.003	0.004	0.005
Ca	0.007	0.004	0.005	0.008	0.004	0.006	0.007	0.008	0.007	0.006	0.006	0.006	0.005
Ni	0.004	0.004	0.006	0.005	0.006	0.006	0.003	0.005	0.002	0.000	0.006	0.006	0.006
Total	3.025	3.017	3.026	3.042	3.027	3.000	3.034	3.007	3.000	3.014	3.001	3.009	3.003
Fo	80.2	84.1	87.3	82.1	85.2	84.7	79.4	85.9	79.2	84.9	85.6	85.6	85.3

FeO*=total iron.

Table 3: Chemical compositions of representative clinopyroxene phenocrysts and microphenocrysts

Unit	SF	SF	F	F	A
Grain no.:					micro
	cpx3	cpx3	cpx1	cpx1	cpx4
Distance from rim (μm)	31	124	97	214	79
<i>wt %</i>					
SiO ₂	42.5	46.6	48.2	46.1	48.8
TiO ₂	4.65	2.75	2.61	2.84	2.35
Al ₂ O ₃	9.86	7.02	5.56	7.96	4.75
FeO*	7.96	6.72	7.03	6.70	6.54
MgO	11.62	13.85	14.46	13.55	15.06
Cr ₂ O ₃	0.00	0.07	0.01	0.14	0.00
MnO	0.10	0.10	0.13	0.09	0.14
CaO	21.88	21.87	21.20	21.59	22.08
Na ₂ O	0.49	0.53	0.38	0.58	0.42
Total	99.0	99.5	99.6	99.5	100.1
<i>O = 6</i>					
Si	1.602	1.729	1.789	1.709	1.796
Ti	0.132	0.077	0.073	0.079	0.065
Al	0.438	0.307	0.243	0.348	0.206
Fe _c ²⁺	0.124	0.093	0.160	0.097	0.100
Mg	0.653	0.766	0.801	0.749	0.827
Cr	0.000	0.002	0.000	0.004	0.000
Mn	0.003	0.003	0.004	0.003	0.004
Ca	0.884	0.869	0.844	0.858	0.871
Na	0.036	0.038	0.027	0.041	0.030
Fe _c ³⁺	0.130	0.118	0.059	0.113	0.103
Total	4.003	4.002	4.001	4.002	4.002
Mg#	84.0	89.2	83.3	88.5	89.2
Mg#*	72.0	78.4	78.5	78.1	80.3
Wo	49.4	47.1	45.3	47.2	45.8
En	36.5	41.5	43.0	41.2	43.5
Fs	14.2	11.4	11.8	11.6	10.7

Mg#=(100xMg/(Mg+Fe²⁺)). Mg#*=(100xMg/(Mg+Fe*)). Wo=(100xCa/(Mg+ Fe*+Ca)).

En=(100xMg/(Mg+ Fe*+Ca)). Fs=(100x(Fe*)/(Mg+ Fe*+Ca)). FeO*=total iron. Fe_c=calculated iron.

Table 4: Calculated times (in days) of the magmatic processes obtained by modelling the chemical diffusion of Fe-Mg, Ni and Ca in olivine crystals.

Unit	Ol	Elem.	P1*	P2*	B2*	α	β	γ	Time 1	Time 2	Time 3	Total Time	$\Delta(-)$	$\Delta(+)$
SF	1	Fo	80	82	79	68	160	87	496		20	516	83	103
SF	1	Ni	0.16	0.20	0.11	68	160	87	494		23	518	100	113
SF	1	Ca	0.27	0.31	0.34	68	160	87	200		455	655	142	174
SF	2	Fo	84	85	80	156	107	74		111	12	123	19	22
SF	2	Ni	0.19	0.26	0.12	156	107	74		149	4	152	26	30
SF	6	Fo	87	85	81	59	135	60		43	6	49	10	9
SF	6	Ni	0.29	0.24	0.13	59	135	60		42	6	48	8	11
SF	6	Ca	0.20	0.26	0.30	59	135	60		33	28	61	11	15
SF	11	Fo	82	80	79	23	111	81	336		3	338	58	70
SF	12	Fo	85	83	80	88	69	160		19	3	22	4	4
F	5	Fo	85	83	77	119	144	70		36	3	40	7	7
F	5	Ni	0.28	0.22	0.11	119	144	70		36	3	39	7	8
F	11	Fo	79	82	78	38	83	127	375		5	380	62	75
F	11	Ni	0.16	0.21	0.10	38	83	127	317		15	331	59	75
F	18	Fo	86	84	78	75	126	39		37	1	38	6	7
F	18	Ni	0.26	0.22	0.14	75	126	39		34	2	36	6	9
A	10	Fo	79	82	79	119	28	88	399		14	413	69	81
A	10	Ni	0.11	0.20	0.09	119	28	88	342		21	363	67	79
A	10	Ca	0.25	0.30	0.32	119	28	88	392		254	646	215	129
A	11	Fo	85	84	80	89	51	141		5	1	6	1	1
A	12	Fo	86	84	79	17	85	106		68	11	79	13	14
A	13	Fo	85	83	77	102	15	99		22	6	28	5	6
A	14	Fo	85	84	79	35	116	69		52	13	65	11	12
A	14	Ni	0.33	0.22	0.06	35	116	69		50	17	67	12	13
A	14	Ca	0.19	0.30	0.32	35	116	69		149	49	198	30	38

*Values of initial and boundary conditions of Fo (mol%), NiO and CaO (wt%). Time1 and 2 correspond to the first two mixing events, and are the lapse time (in days) between the initial condition (P1) and the first boundary condition (P2). Time3 is the third mixing event and the rise of magma to the surface and records the lapse of time between the first and the second boundary conditions (P2 and B2, respectively). Olivines with Fo \geq 83 have been modelled considering T=1245 \pm 15 °C, P=5 kbar and Δ NNO=0, while olivines with Fo \leq 82 have been modelled for T=1175 \pm 15 °C, P=2 kbar and Δ NNO=0. $\Delta(-)$ and $\Delta(+)$ are the errors on the total time calculated by DIPRA (Girona & Costa, 2013) after the anisotropy correction.

Table 5: Factual accounts of the unrest activity preceding the eruptions of Siete Fuetnes (SF), Fasnía (F) and Arafo (A) reported in historical documents

Chronological range	Days before and after the eruption			Event	Localities	
	SF	F	A			
1704	December					
	24	-7	-12	-40	Low but continuous ground shaking. Twenty nine earthquakes in three hours. Panic stricken people. Houses shaken. The population leaves the houses.	LO, PC, LR
	25	-6	-11	-39	Increase of ground shaking. 23 earthquakes before the afternoon (some of them strong). Panic stricken people. Houses shaken. The population left the houses.	G, C, A
	26	-5	-10	-38	Earthquakes every two or three hours (some of them strong).	LO, PC, LR, G, C, A
	27	-4	-9	-37	Earthquakes every two or three hours (some of them strong). Three in one hour. Houses shaken, panic-stricken people. People realize that seismicity might be due to a volcano. Innumerable earthquakes during the night. The population sleeps outdoors.	LO, PC, LR, G, C, A
	28	-3	-8	-36	Some earthquakes, some of them strong. Some houses damaged. Panic stricken people, especially in La Orotava.	LO, PC, LR
	29-30	-1	-6	-34	Some earthquakes, mainly small.	LO, PC, LR
	31	0	-5	-33	Some earthquakes. SIETE FUENTES ERUPTION.	LO, PC, LR
1705	January					
	2	2	-3	-31	Six strong earthquakes and some small ones	LO, PC, LR
	3	3	-2	-30	Small earthquakes. Also the volcanic activity reduces.	LO, PC, LR
	4	4	-1	-29	Earthquakes every hour.	LO, PC, LR
	5	5	0	-28	Two very strong earthquakes in five hours. Collapses in cliffs and mountains. Panic stricken people. Houses strongly shaken and damaged (many collapsed). The population sleeps outdoors. FASNIA ERUPTION. (End SIETE FUENTES ERUPTION?).	LO
	8-10	10	5	-23	Many earthquakes, some of them strong. Continuous ground shaking.	LO, PC, LR
	11	11	6	-22	Many earthquakes. Four strong. Continuous ground shaking.	LO, PC, LR
	12	12	7	-21	Many earthquakes, one very strong. Continuous ground shaking.	LO, PC, LR
	13	13	8	-20	Four earthquakes in one hour. Two earthquakes very strong in the afternoon. The population thinks another vent has opened. Continuous ground shaking. One earthquake at midnight very strong and long. Some earthquakes during the night.	LO, PC, LR
	14-15	15	10	-18	Many earthquakes. (End FASNIA ERUPTION?).	LO, PC, LR
	16	16	11	-17	(End FASNIA ERUPTION?).	
	17	17	12	-16	One earthquake very strong and long. Collapse of some houses. Panic stricken people. Strongest effects in La Orotava.	LO
	19	19	14	-14	Many small earthquakes and some strong. One earthquake very strong.	LO, PC, LR
	20	20	15	-13	Many small earthquakes and some strong. One earthquake very strong and long.	LO, PC, LR
	21	21	16	-12	Many small earthquakes and some strong. One of the stronger earthquakes up to this date. So many strong earthquakes during the night that they were not counted. The population sleeps in the churches.	LO, PC, LR

1									
2									
3		22	22	17	-11	Twenty strong and smaller earthquakes. Two earthquakes very strong in two hours. Continuous ground shaking during the night.	LO, PC, LR		
4									
5		23	23	18	-10	Some small earthquakes.	LO, PC, LR		
6									
7		24	24	19	-9	Many small earthquakes and some strong. Two earthquakes very strong in the morning. In the afternoon one earthquake very strong: collapse of many houses. Collapses in some cliffs and mountains.	LO, PC, LR		
8									
9		25	25	20	-8	Some small earthquakes. Loud noise in the mountains and smoking areas. Some collapses in cliffs and mountains. People expect another eruption.	LO, PC, LR		
10									
11		26-27	27	22	-6	Some small earthquakes.	LO, PC, LR		
12									
13		28	28	23	-5	Many earthquakes. Two of the strongest and longest earthquakes in the morning. Other earthquakes very strong during the night.	LO, PC, LR		
14									
15		29	29	24	-4	Many strong and long earthquakes (so many that they could not be counted). Continuous ground shaking.	LO, PC, LR		
16									
17		30	30	25	-3	Many strong and long earthquakes (so many that they could not be counted). Continuous ground shaking. Big smoking cavity opened close to Güimar, loud noise from it. People expect a new volcano.	LO, PC, LR		
18									
19		31	31	26	-2	Many strong earthquakes. Panic stricken people. The population sleeps outdoors.	LO, PC, LR		
20	1705	February							
21		1	32	27	-1	(?) No earthquakes during this day. Conflicting reports.			
22									
23		2	33	28	0	Many strong earthquakes. Houses shaken (collapse of some buildings). People fall down because of the ground shaking. Panic stricken people. People expect a new volcano. Very strong earthquake felt in the upper valley between Güimar and Arafo: ARAFO ERUPTION.	LO, PC, LR		
24									
25		3	34	29	1	Two strong earthquakes felt in the whole island. Collapse of some houses. People relate these earthquakes with the opening of a new vent in the volcano. People fall down because of the ground shaking. Panic stricken people. Collapses in cliffs and mountains.	LO, PC, LR		
26									
27		4-28	59	54	26	Seismic activity continues.	LO, PC, LR		
28	1705	March							
29		1-27	86	81	53	Seismic activity continues. End of ARAFO ERUPTION on March 27th.			

LO, La Orotava; PC, Puerto de la Cruz; LR, Los Realejos; A, Arafo; C, Candelaria; G, Güimar.